

Deliverable D7.4 Data management plan

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OPTIPATH

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D7.4 Data Management Plan

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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

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Abstract
This document presents the Data Management Plan for the EIC OPTIPATH project 101185769

Public introduction
The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to contribute to good data handling by describing what research data the project expects to use, data handling principles, and an assessment of what data can be shared with the public or why data cannot be open. Furthermore, it gives instructions on naming conventions and metadata structure.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN	
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Version:	1.0

Release history		
Version	Date	Version description
0.1	2025-07-09	Draft DMP distributed to OPTIPATH consortium
1.0	2025-07-21	First version DMP submitted through the SyGMa portal

Table of contents

List of Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations	5
Executive Summary.....	7
1 Introduction and data summary.....	8
1.1 Introduction	8
1.1.1 Purpose of the document.....	8
1.1.2 Intended readership	8
1.1.3 Structure of this document.....	8
1.1.4 Relationship with other deliverables.....	8
1.2 Data Summary.....	9
1.2.1 Purpose of the data collection and generation	9
1.2.2 Data types, formats and size	9
1.2.2.1 Types of data	9
1.2.2.2 Data formats.....	10
1.2.2.3 Size of data.....	10
1.2.3 Origin of data and provenance	10
1.2.4 Potential reuse of data	10
1.2.5 Data storing in active project – project platform	10
1.2.6 Data Repository	11
1.2.7 Instructions for uploading datasets to project platform and chosen repository	11
2 FAIR Data Management.....	13
2.1 Making data findable	13
2.1.1 OPTIPATH Community in Zenodo.....	13
2.1.2 Metadata in Zenodo	13
2.1.3 Versioning and Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)	13
2.1.4 Approach to search keywords	14
2.1.5 Naming conventions.....	14
2.2 Making data accessible	14
2.3 Making data interoperable	17
2.4 Reusable data.....	17
2.4.1 Recommended Creative Commons (CC) licences.....	17
2.4.2 Availability and longevity of the OPTIPATH research data sets	17
3 Other research outputs.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
4 Allocation of resources	17
5 Data Security.....	18
5.1 Active Project - Data security as specified for SINTEF SharePoint.....	18
5.2 Repository - Data security as specified for Zenodo	18

6 Ethical Aspects 19
6.1 Contact information..... 19

7 References 20

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Process for uploading datasets 12

List of Tables

Table 1: List of abbreviations..... 5

Table 2: Instructions for uploading datasets to SharePoint 11

Table 3: Expected datasets in OPTIPATH..... 15

List of Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 1: List of abbreviations

Term	Explanation
BibTeX	A reference management software for formatting lists of references.
CC licence	Creative Commons licenses are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. ¹
CC BY	This CC-license lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon your work, even commercially, if they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.
CC0	CC0 enables scientists, educators, artists and other creators and owners of copyright- or database-protected content to waive those interests in their works and thereby place them as completely as possible in the public domain, so that others may freely build upon, enhance, and reuse the works for any purposes without restriction under copyright or database rights.
CC BY-NC	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work non-commercially, and although their new work must also acknowledge you and be non-commercial, they don't have to license their derivative works on the same terms.
CC BY-SA	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, if they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to "copyleft" free and open source software licenses. All new works based on yours will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use.
CSL	Citation Style Language An open XML-based standard to format citations and bibliographies.
Deliverable type	R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports) DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. OTHER: Software, technical diagram
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable data
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation. Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation An open-standard file format.
MARCXML	An XML schema based on the common MARC21 standards
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting.
Research data	Refers to information, facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of

¹ Creative Commons homepage: <https://creativecommons.org/>

Term	Explanation
	data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings, and images.
REST API	REST is an architectural style that defines a set of constraints to be used for creating web services. API stands for Application Programming Interface
SSL/TLS	Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security These are protocols offering secure communication on the internet.
Zenodo	Zenodo is a catch-all research data repository that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share research results, make research results citable, and search and reuse open research results from other projects. Zenodo is harvested by the OpenAIRE portal and hosted by the CERN cloud infrastructure.

Executive Summary

About the EIC OPTIPATH project: Treatment decisions for many pathological conditions, including inflammatory, degenerative, autoimmune, infectious diseases, and cancer, are largely based on microscopy study of the surgically excised tissue specimens (histology). OPTIPATH provides a new paradigm for gathering objective optical tissue-dependent data, which is essential to overcoming the diagnostic challenges of inter-observer variability and limited sensitivity and specificity. OPTIPATH will offer non-destructive, label-free, real-time, 3D-presentation of tissue samples. This is enabled by (i) revolutionary nano-photonics optical metasurfaces (OMS) for simultaneous single-shot acquisition of spectral and polarimetric information, and adaptive OMS actuated by thin-film piezoelectric Micro-Electro-Mechanical-Systems (MEMS) for (ii) rapid Vector Vortex Beam (VVB) shaping of light, and (iii) rapid confocal 3D imaging. The wealth of objective diagnostic data provided will be interpreted using Machine Learning (ML) / Deep Learning (DL) and is essential to overcome inter-observer variability in diagnosis and provide actionable insights to the clinician. By utilizing optical markers present in unprepared tissue histological procedures can be dramatically sped up, offering real-time diagnosis in operation theatres and pathology departments. By offering timely and accurate diagnosis, OPTIPATH will enable early diagnosis and improved prognosis of recovery.

The purpose of the DMP is to contribute to good data handling by describing what research data the project expects to use, data handling principles, and an assessment of what data can be shared with the public or why data cannot be open. Furthermore, it gives instructions on naming conventions and metadata structure.

Ethical aspects related to data collection, generation and sharing have been considered. All datasets will be uploaded, stored and handled in accordance with national and European rules on data protection and privacy. Metadata will be added to all datasets, and instructions on how to upload, store, publish and preserve research data is provided in this document.

OPTIPATH will use Zenodo², a trusted and OpenAire compliant data repository to comply with the FAIR data principles.

Each dataset will be given a persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, DOI), supplied with relevant metadata, and linked to the project acronym, full project name and grant agreement number. Publications and underlying research data will be linked, and a Creative Commons license will regulate reuse of the OPTIPATH research data. Data security arrangements are defined.

The DMP is a living document and will be updated as the project proceeds. The final version of the DMP will be made available at the end of the project. It will include instructions for how to access and reuse open research data from OPTIPATH.

² OPTIPATH Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/optipath>

1 Introduction and data summary

1.1 Introduction

1.1.1 Purpose of the document

The DMP provides an overview of research data the project is expected to generate or reuse, the types and formats of this data, and how this data is processed and stored to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, according to the principles of FAIR data management. The purpose of the DMP is to contribute to good data handling during the project's lifetime, and to describe how the research data will be curated and preserved.

1.1.2 Structure of this document

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 is an introduction chapter describing the main purpose, structure and intended readership of the DMP and an overview of the research data in the OPTIPATH.
- Section 2 describes how the OPTIPATH will comply with the FAIR data principles.
- Section 3 gives an overview of other research outputs that are generated/re-used in the project.
- Section 4 describes the allocation of resources.
- Section 5 gives a detailed description of data security arrangements.
- Section 6 deals with ethical aspects related to data management in the OPTIPATH.
- Section 7 is references.

The online tool DMPOnline, hosted by Data Curation Centre, has been used to generate content for this document³. The tool is based on the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#) and guidelines for FAIR data.

1.1.3 Intended readership

In the project:

- Project participants who are responsible for, or in any way involved with, data collection and data handling can use this document for instructions on how to handle, store and process data.
- All project participants can use this document to get an overview of data collected in the project and how this is processed, stored and made accessible.

External audience:

- The **Data Summary** and **FAIR Data Management** sections can be used by all relevant stakeholders who are interested in OPTIPATH related activities and research topics to get an overview of the data collected in the project, how to access this data, and, if applicable, how to re-use this data in their own activities.

1.1.4 Relationship with other deliverables

The DMP is not a fixed document but evolves during the lifespan of the project. Deliverable D7.5 *RP2 update of the Data Management Plan* will be the final version of the OPTIPATH Data Management Plan, due 31st of January 2028.

This document complements the following deliverables:

³ https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/about_us

- D7.3 Plan for Dissemination and Communication Activities
- D7.2 Plan for Exploitation Activities

1.2 Data Summary

Table 3 provides a list of all types of data currently expected to be generated in the OPTIPATH and their planned accessibility. We recognise that this list will develop and grow as the project evolves. Adhering to the Open Sciences practice of “As open as possible, as closed as necessary” most data is determined to be sensitive at its outset, but will be made openly available when possible (e.g. upon publication of results, or after IPR has been secured).

All or parts of annotated sets of histological images from the HO2020 Cascade Funded ATTRACT Phase 2 MetaHiLight and ATTRACT Phase 1 SmartOpsy will be considered for use in the project.

1.2.1 Purpose of the data collection and generation

The overall motivation for data collection in OPTIPATH is to develop optical components that can collect a wealth of optical objective diagnostic data and translate this into actionable insights through the use of Machine Learning (ML) / Deep Learning (DL). To achieve these goals the project aims to design and develop radical optical technologies, which also involves the collection and analysis of a wealth of simulation data.

Only data that is needed to perform project activities will be collected, and as far as possible, participants will not be asked to provide personal data unless this is necessary.

1.2.2 Data types, formats and size

1.2.2.1 Types of data

The OPTIPATH will collect, generate and reuse various types of data, such as:

- Observations and collected data
 - Sensor data
 - Existing data from open sources (e.g. literature reviews, databases, statistics, etc.)
- Calculation data (data from models, simulations, and other calculations)
- Experimental data (results from controlled trials or test data)
 - Images containing optical signatures from tissue (mouse models and samples from biobanks).
- Algorithms, scripts
 - Machine Learning and Deep Learning scripts.

Data will be organised in datasets according to type and content of the data.

We currently do not envision that OPTIPATH will collect personal data. If some of the data OPTIPATH will collect and generate can be classified as personal data, such as names, IP addresses, residence of participants etc, this data must be irreversibly anonymised before being made public. If such data cannot be irreversibly anonymised, it will remain confidential and only managed by designated Data Controllers in the project. If a partner who is not a Data Controller needs access to process personal data (Data Processor), an assessment of this will be done by the Data Controller and if granted a specific Data Processing Agreement will be set up between the Data Controller and the partner requesting access. Non-anonymous data, although not openly shared in the project or beyond, can still provide input to deliverables and publications. Only anonymised data or analysis of the aggregated data, containing no details that can be linked to individual participants, will be made public.

1.2.2.2 Data formats

The OPTIPATH will preferentially use widely accepted formats for data generation, such as:

List what is relevant for your project.

- Documents/Reports/Publications: .PDF/A, .txt, .doc/docx
- Spreadsheets: .xls/.xlsx
- Databases: .csv
- Audio files: .mp3, .wav, .wma, .ra
- Pictures: .jpg, .png, .tiff.
- Video: .avi, .flv, .mov, .mp4, .wmv

1.2.2.3 Size of data

We envision that the main challenge will be the size of the sets of acquired images, which may accumulate to require considerable space. Zenodo has a default limit of 50GB per dataset, with a maximum of 100 files per record. Users can apply for a one-time quota increase to 200GB on a case-by-case basis. At the moment this seems sufficient, but we will consider alternatives if this proves to be an issue.

1.2.3 Origin of data and provenance

Data background which the partners have acquired in previous research projects, and to which access rights already exist, may be utilized. These include

- Parts of annotated sets of histological images from the HO2020 Cascade Funded ATTRACT Phase 2 MetaHiLight and ATTRACT Phase 1 SmartOpsy.
- Simulation outputs from external and internally funded projects in the various organizations to which the partners belong.

1.2.4 Potential reuse of data

We envision that the both raw images with optical signatures (spectral, polarization, depth information, etc) and annotated images can be re-used for the training of machine learning and deep learning algorithms. As such the data has potential reuse within bio-optical and medical disciplines.

1.2.5 Data storing in active project – project platform

All datasets in the OPTIPATH will be stored in a SINTEF SharePoint project site. This will be the projects online working and collaboration area during 36 months the project is active.

All partners will be responsible for uploading datasets they have collected/generated during the project. Each dataset will be uploaded to a dedicated research data folder in the SharePoint site, thus providing an overview of all datasets relevant to that activity/task. All datasets will use standard SharePoint version control and access control is available to enable limited access to certain types of data.

These metadata will be provided for each data set:

- Project ID (Grant No)
- Data Owner
- File name
- Version
- WP number
- File type
- Date/time
- Dissemination level
- Keyword

1.2.6 Data Repository

The OPTIPATH project will use Zenodo, a trusted and OpenAire compliant repository to comply with the FAIR principles. All scientific publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets will be uploaded to the OPTIPATH Community² in the repository. In addition, the project will upload other datasets (not directly linked to publications and deliverables) with dissemination level "Public" and make them openly accessible via the repository.

1.2.7 Instructions for uploading datasets to project platform and chosen repository

Table 2 and Figure 1 provide instructions to project participants on how to upload datasets to SharePoint and the Zenodo:

Table 2: Instructions for uploading datasets to SharePoint

Upload instructions - OPTIPATH SharePoint Site
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please upload all OPTIPATH data sets to the relevant folders (designated by WP and Task numbers) in the OPTIPATH SharePoint site. • Use this naming convention (for details see 2.1.5): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ YYYY-MM-DD_DeliverableNumber/TaskNumber_Descriptive text_v<version number> ○ YYYY-MM-DD_Descriptive text_v<version number> • Be sure to use the same file name when uploading later versions • Register mandatory metadata on your data set.
Upload instructions – Data Repository
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data underlying scientific publications/classified as "Public" should, in addition, be uploaded to Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/optipath/). To do this you must complete the following steps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create a profile in Zenodo to be able to upload files ○ Click on the <i>OPTIPATH Community</i> link above, or search for "<i>OPTIPATH Community</i>" under the "Communities" tab at the top of the Zenodo site ○ On the Community site, click the green "New upload" button in the top right corner ○ Enter requested data and confirm the upload. ○ Remember to add the European Commission community in the box labelled "communities". You can use the search function to locate the community and add it. The data will then automatically be uploaded to both communities, so you don't have to do it twice. • Uploading should be done as soon as possible and at the latest on article publication or EC approval of deliverables for underlying datasets. Other datasets will be uploaded in the final month of the project at the latest. • Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets collected/generated by them. If needed, the relevant task leader in the relevant WP may be requested to supply assistance.

Figure 1: Process for uploading datasets

2 FAIR Data Management

OPTIPATH will manage data in accordance with the principles of FAIR data management⁴ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data). The project aims to maximise access to, and re-use of research data generated by the project.

At the same time, there are datasets, or parts of datasets, generated in this project that cannot be shared:

- to allow for protection of results prior to commercial exploitation
- to protect business sensitive information
- to protect confidential/classified information

Table 3 provides a current overview of the expected types of data in the OPTIPATH and their accessibility. By default, most data are designated sensitive to allow for evaluation of the above before making public.

2.1 Making data findable

2.1.1 OPTIPATH Community in Zenodo

OPTIPATH will use the Zenodo repository as the main tool to make our research data findable in accordance with the FAIR data principles.

A *OPTIPATH* community² has been established in the repository, and the project will upload all our public datasets and deliverables as well as scientific publications to this community. This will ensure harvesting of project results by OpenAire and provide maximum findability. All uploads will be enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number, Project Name and Acronym. The repository provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements.

2.1.2 Metadata in Zenodo

Metadata associated with each published data set in Zenodo will by default be as follows:

- Digital Object Identifiers
- Version numbers
- Creator (Name and ORCID)
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information
- Access and licensing info
- Language

In addition, we will add the project name and GA number

2.1.3 Versioning and Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)

Zenodo provides DOI versioning of all datasets uploaded to their communities, which allows us to edit and update the uploaded datasets after they have been published. This also allows us to cite specific versions of an upload and cite all versions of an upload.

⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

2.1.4 Approach to search keywords

Each partner who collects and generates public datasets will be responsible for uploading these to the repository and to assign specific search keywords relevant for these datasets. Dataset specific keywords must be descriptive to the content of the dataset.

2.1.5 Naming conventions

Data will be named using the following naming conventions:

- YYYY-MM-DD_DeliverableNumber/TaskNumber_Descriptive text_v<version number>
- YYYY-MM-DD_Descriptive text_v<version number>

Explanation of the naming convention:

- "YYYY-MM-DD" refers to the date at which the document was created
- "DeliverableNumber/TaskNumber" refers to the deliverable or task number as described in the DoA
- "Descriptive text" refers to a *short* description of the content of the dataset (see example)
- v<version number> refers to the version number of the document

Example of dataset name:

2025-06-30_D7.2_Data_management_plan_v1

2025-06-30_MEMO_metasurface_design_v2

2.2 Making data accessible

The EU's Open Science Policy aims to make research data generated by Horizon Europe projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protection of personal or sensitive data due to privacy concerns and/or commercial or security reasons.

All public datasets, scientific publications and deliverables will be uploaded to [Zenodo](#) and made openly available, free of charge. Publications and underlying data sets will be linked through use of persistent identifiers (DOI versioning). Data sets with dissemination level "confidential" (e.g. non-anonymous datasets) will not be shared due to privacy/security/ethical concerns, or more likely, some datasets might be restricted due to protection for commercial exploitation.

Metadata including licences for individual data records as well as record collections will be harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application. OPTIPATH will aim for no specific software or hardware being needed to access and reuse the data.

Table 3 below provides a list of types of datasets expected to be generated in the OPTIPATH and their planned accessibility. This list constitutes the first version of dataset description, and we recognise that it will develop and grow as the project evolves. In addition, some information concerning the datasets currently remain unknown, e.g. size of the datasets. An updated version of the list containing all dataset details will be provided at the end of the project.

Table 3: Expected data in OPTIPATH

WP	Task	Type of dataset	Description/Purpose	Format	Responsible	Origin	Class	Comments
1	1.2	Specifications and Key Performance Indicators	Requirements concerning optical sensor sensing modalities, control electronics, etc.	.docx	UiO	Consortium	SEN	Confidential, due to commercial reasons. Upon publication relevant parts of the simulation results will be made public.
2	2.2-2.4	Simulation outputs of turbid media light scattering modelling	Theoretical and computational studies of how the fundamental properties of VVBs are changed due to interaction with tissue samples.	.csv, .mat, etc	ASTON	Monte Carlo-based simulations	SEN	Confidential, due to commercial reasons. Upon publication relevant parts of the simulation results will be made public.
3	3.3-3.4	Annotation and classification of images of tissue	Machine learning approaches such as Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, or/and Deep Learning will be used.	.csv, .mat	OULU	Measurements	SEN	Confidential, due to commercial reasons. Upon publication relevant parts of the simulation results will be made public.
4	4.1-4.3	Simulation outputs of light manipulation modelling	Simulations of optical properties such as phase and transmissivity, relying on tools such as FEM, FDTD, RCWA.	.mph, JSON, .csv, .mat, plots (.png),	SDU	Commercial software such as COMSOL, Lumerical	SEN	Confidential, due to commercial reasons. Upon publication relevant parts of the simulation results will be made public.
5	5.1	Simulation outputs of MEMS mechanical modelling	Simulations of resonance frequencies, displacement rangers, etc.	.mph, .csv, plots (.png)	SINTEF	Commercial COMSOL software	SEN	Confidential, due to commercial reasons. Upon publication relevant parts of the simulation results will be made public.
6	6.1-6.3	Annotation and classification of images of tissue. Classifying	Characterizing tissue using the optical signatures. Prediction of tissue sub-regions using		UiO		SEN	Confidential, due to commercial reasons. Upon publication relevant

		tissue sub-regions, diagnosis of diseases	annotations and ML procedures. Prediction of diagnostic features and diagnoses based on multidimensional optical information.					parts of the simulation results will be made public.
7	7.1-7.2	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation		.doc, .ppt	SINTEF		SEN	Confidential until IPR strategy is defined due to commercial reasons. Upon publication relevant parts of the simulation results will be made public.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Zenodo uses JSON schema as the internal representation of metadata and offers export to other formats such as Dublin Core, MARCXML, BibTeX, CSL, DataCite and export to Mendeley. The data record metadata will utilise the vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Reference to any external metadata is done with a resolvable URL.

2.4 Reusable data

The OPTIPATH will enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) all public data sets, and regulate this by using Creative Commons Licences.

2.4.1 Recommended Creative Commons (CC) licences

OPTIPATH will use Creative Commons (CC) licences, which are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. As a default, the CC BY license will be applied for public OPTIPATH research data. This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you. This does not preclude the use of less restrictive licenses as CC 0 or more restrictive licenses as CC BY-ND, which does not allow derivations.

Application of licences will be assessed on a case-by-basis in close collaboration with the Coordinator, Innovation Manager and partners concerned.

2.4.2 Availability and longevity of the OPTIPATH research data sets

Public (anonymous) data

For data published in scientific journals, the underlying data will be made available no later than by journal publication. The data will be linked to the publication. Data associated with public deliverables will be shared once the deliverable has been approved and accepted by the EC. For other public datasets not directly linked to a scientific publication or deliverable, such datasets will be made available upon assessment by the responsible partner that it is ready for publishing, and in the final month of the project at the latest.

Open data can be reused in accordance with the Creative Commons licences. Data classified as confidential will not be reusable due to privacy/security/commercial concerns.

The public data will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years. This is currently the lifetime stated by the host laboratory CERN. If Zenodo has to close their operations, they have provided a guarantee that they will migrate all content (including metadata) to other suitable repositories.

Confidential (non-anonymous) data

All non-anonymous data will be deleted at the end of the project.

3 Allocation of resources

OPTIPATH uses standard tools and a free of charge research data repository. The costs of data management activities are limited to project management costs and will be covered by allocated resources in the project budget.

Long-term preservation of the public data is ensured through Zenodo. Other resources needed to support reuse of data after the project ends will be solved on a case-by-case basis.

4 Data Security

In this chapter, the security features of the research data infrastructure used to store and handle data in the OPTIPATH project are described.

4.1 Active Project - Data security as specified for SINTEF SharePoint

SINTEF SharePoint is the online collaboration platform used the OPTIPATH project. A dedicated project site has been established on this platform, accessible only by the partner representatives in the consortium.

The OPTIPATH SharePoint site has the following security settings:

- Access level: Restricted to persons (project members only). Further access restrictions on specific folders could if necessary be enabled.
- Encryption with SSL/TLS protects data transfer between partners and the SINTEF SharePoint site.
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevents and/or registers possible manipulation of data.

Documents and elements in the SINTEF SharePoint sites are stored in Microsoft's cloud solutions, based in Ireland and the Netherlands. There will be no use of data centres in the US or outside EU/EEA and associated countries⁵.

Nightly back-ups are handled by SINTEF's IT operations contractor. As a baseline, all project data will be stored for 10 years according to SINTEF's ICT policy, unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.

4.2 Repository - Data security as specified for Zenodo

The following list describes the security settings for Zenodo:

- Versions: Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and records are preserved.
- Replicas: All data files are stored in the CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.
- Retention period: Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. The host laboratory of Zenodo CERN, has defined a lifetime for the repository of the next 20 years minimum.
- Functional preservation: Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.
- File preservation: Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.
- Fixity and authenticity: All data files are stored along with an MD5 checksum of the file content.
- Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.

⁵ EEA = Norway, Iceland, Liechtenstein

- Succession plans: In case of closure of the repository, a guarantee has been made from Zenodo to migrate all content to suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

5 Ethical Aspects

The proposed work in OPTIPATH will fully comply with the regulations set out in Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁶. In addition, OPTIPATH complies with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless country in which research is carried out.

Nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules and norms regarding ethics in conducting research.

SINTEF follows the Vancouver Recommendations for publication of scientific work.

5.1 Contact information

Use of e-mail addresses in OPTIPATH SharePoint Site:

An e-mail address is by definition personal information and covered by GDPR. The e-mail addresses of project participants are stored in the OPTIPATH SharePoint Site. Only the project participants invited will have access. The e-mail address is a prerequisite to access the projects working area. By accepting the SharePoint invitation, the participants consent to use and store their e-mail address for the purpose of online collaboration in the project.

The email-addresses will be deleted when access to the project area is no longer needed (1 year after project closure).

SINTEF has signed GDPR data processing agreements with both Microsoft and the IT operations contractor handling our SharePoint platform.

Currently, no ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data generation and sharing have been identified. Ethical and legal aspects related to research data generated by the project will be considered as the work proceeds.

5.2 Pictures and videos for communication purposes

OPTIPATH will collect pictures and videos for use in communication activities (website, newsletter, social media). Such data will only be collected with prior consent from the people involved and only used for as long as consent is given. Pictures and video can contain personal data if an individual is the focus of the image or video. Examples include: 1) pictures/video of individuals stored together with personal details (e.g. identity cards); 2) pictures/video of individuals posted on the project website along with biographical details; 3) individual images published in a newsletter. Examples of pictures and video that is unlikely to contain personal data are: 1) pictures/video where people are incidentally included in an image or are not the focus (e.g. at a big conference/workshop); 2) images of people who are no longer alive (the GDPR only applies to living people).

When collecting pictures and video OPTIPATH will follow established guidance and best practice on collecting and processing such data to ensure that we adhere to the legal requirements. Under no

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

circumstances will pictures containing personal information be publicly shared without the subject's explicit consent.

5.3 General comments

The OPTIPATH partners are obliged by European and national law (GDPR) to protect personal data.

The coordinator of the OPTIPATH, SINTEF, follows ethical guidelines in its work, and all work conducted by SINTEF is subject to the SINTEF Ethics Council and the appointed Ethics Representative. SINTEF will also ensure that all participants in the OPTIPATH follows the ethical guidelines of SINTEF. Important aspects with respect to this are:

- The ethical guidelines are based on the vision of using science and technology to create a better society and are reviewed continuously to ensure they stay up to date with developments in society and the challenges of today. They generally fall into these categories: research ethics, business ethics, and ethics in interpersonal relationships.
- SINTEF is a member of the UN Global Compact and Transparency International, and SINTEF's ethics are guided by the principles highlighted by these organisations, as well as based on the regulations of the national ethics committees, the principles promoted by the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE), and on international conventions such as the Vancouver Convention. When dilemmas of research ethics require an assessment beyond the scope of our guidelines, our Ethics Council and Ethics Representative, we refer to statements from the EGE.
- All SINTEF's employees are expected to act in accordance with the ethical guidelines and principles. As coordinator of the OPTIPATH project, SINTEF will ensure that any ethical issues, which may arise, will be handled appropriately and in a transparent and fair manner.

6 References

European Commission. *H2020 Programme. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.0, 26 July 2016

European Commission. *Horizon 2020 Programme. Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.2, 21 March 2017

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC